

plant was 154.4% for Jhona 3491/IR6. This was based on simultaneous heterosis in plant height, number of productive tillers per plant, panicle

length, total florets per panicle, and 1,000-grain weight. Heterosis for yield for the best 4 crosses varied greatly from 13.9 to 154.4%.

Results indicate the potential for harnessing hybrid vigor in the development of relatively salt-tolerant strains of rice. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

CN704-7-3, a new variety for rainfed deepwater areas in eastern India

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Based on national performance in 1984-86, the 1986 annual rice workshop at Hyderabad recommended CN704-7-3

(IET9060) from the cross Pankaj/CN540 developed at RRS, for areas where water stagnates up to 100 cm during wet season (kharif) in West Bengal and Bihar. In six state adaptive trials in 1982-85, CN704-7-3 outyielded the checks Tilokkachari and Mahsuri by 25% (see table). CN704-7-3 yielded better than check 1 at several water depths (see figure).

CN704-7-3 is photoperiod sensitive

Performance of CN704-7-3 in state and national trials. India, 1982-86.

Trial and year	Site	Max water depth ^a (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
			CN704-7-3	Local check		
State adaptive	1982	Chinsurah	70	3.2	2.4	Tilokkachari
		Nimpith	60	3.6	2.8	Mahsuri
	1983	Hooghly	75	3.8	2.9	Mahsuri
		Chinsurah	75	3.9	2.9	Tilokkachari
	1984	Narendrapur	55	3.4	2.6	Mahsuri
1985	Burdwan	75	3.7	2.6	Mahsuri	
National PVT-5	1984	Cuttack	na	2.5	1.0	CR210-1018
		Bhubaneswar	25	2.0	1.4	OR1 104
		Patna	65	2.1	1.7	Janki
		Sabour	na	3.2	3.0	Janki
UVT-5	1985	Cuttack	na	3.3	3.1	CR1030
		Bhubaneswar	na	1.8	2.0	Khajuriachaur
		Chinsurah	65	3.0	2.0	Tilokkachari
		Karimgunj	na	3.2	2.5	na
		Malda	70	3.6	3.0	CN540
		Ghagraghat	60	2.9	2.0	Madhukar
		Patna	na	2.7	1.8	na
		Arundhutinagar	na	4.9	4.5	Pizam
Physiology screening		Calcutta	60	4.7	4.6	Pankaj
		Chinsurah	65	2.1	0.9	Mahsuri
		Cuttack	55	2.7	2.2	CR1018
		Patna	50	3.4	3.0	IET8879
		Titabar	50	3.5	3.1	Manoharsali
UVT-5	1986	Chinsurah	110	3.0	1.1	TCA212
		Malda	62	3.6	3.2	CN540
		Pusa	85	2.2	1.8	TCA214
		Ranital	65	2.2	1.7	CR1030
		Faizabad	80	1.3	2.0	Pankaj
Physiology screening		Cuttack	50	4.3	3.4	CR1018
		Patna	50	3.2	2.2	Janki
Mean (30 sites)				3.1	2.4	

^a na = data not available.

Yield performance of CN704-7-3 in different water regimes. Chinsurah, India, 1982-86.

and flowers 26-30 Oct. Depending on water depth, it reaches 150-175 cm height with 10-12 tillers/hill. The variety has very good submergence tolerance, kneeing ability, and drought tolerance at early vegetative stage. The panicle is about 22 cm long with good exertion, each accommodating about 175 grains. Grain is medium and bold (length-5.6 mm, breadth-2.8 mm, L:B-2.0) and 1,000-grain weight is 25 g. It possesses yellow hull at maturity, red kernel, and strong seed dormancy. The variety is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and moderately susceptible to blast.

CN704-7-3 yielded 3.1 t/ha (2.4 t/ha for check) in 30 locations and has been recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers' fields. □

Improved basmati donors

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Traditional basmati rices have tall plants, droopy leaves, high lodging tendency, relatively low grain weight,

Yield and quality characteristics of improved basmati donors. Hyderabad, India, 1988.

Character	Pusa 367-152 (Pusa 167-2/Type 3)	Pusa 615-140-10-10 (IET10364) (Pusa 167/Karnal Local)	Pusa 751-1-2 (Pusa 367-4-2-2/Type 3)	Traditional local varieties		
				Karnal Local	Basmati 370	Type 3
Plant height (cm)	80-85	90-95	90-100	135-150	135-150	135-150
Growth duration (d)	145-150	135-140	140-145	145-150	135-140	135-140
Yield (t/ha)	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	2.5-3.0	2.0-2.5	2.0-3.0	2.0-3.0
Test grain weight (g)	25.92	22.80	27.54	22.00	20.53	18.60
Length of milled rice (mm)	7.63	6.98	8.37	7.35	6.87	6.71
Breadth of milled rice (mm)	2.00	1.70	1.90	1.78	1.89	1.84
L:B ratio	3.81	4.11	4.40	4.13	3.63	3.64
Length of kernel after cooking (mm)	16.20	14.70	18.37	13.89	13.64	13.22
Elongation ratio	2.12	2.01	2.19	1.89	1.98	1.97
Alkali spreading value	4	4	4	4	4	4
Amylose (%)	24.00	28.00	24.50	25.50	22.00	22.50
Presence of aroma ^a	M.S.	S	S.S.	S	S	S

^a M.S. = mildly scented, S = scented, S.S. = strongly scented.

and low grain number. In spite of poor yield, their unique cooking quality fetches the highest premium in the national and international markets.

Karnal Local, Basmati 370, and Type 3 are the most widely cultivated varieties. However, Karnal Local's higher kernel length and higher length:breadth ratio give it preference in the market.

After two decades of intensive

convergent breeding with rigorous screening and selection, IARI has developed three promising basmati lines: Pusa 367-152, Pusa 615-140-10-1, and Pusa 751-1-2 (see table). Pusa 367-152 has excellent plant type with stiff stem and dark green erect leaves. It has desirable cooking qualities; however, grain shattering, late maturity, and mild aroma are drawbacks. Pusa 615-140-10-1 has good plant type and all important

basmati components, but with relatively higher amylose content. Pusa 751-1-2 is much superior to traditional basmati in cooking quality and aroma but does not yield well because of low grain number and relatively moderate tillering.

Among them, Pusa 615-140-10-1 (IET10364) has been selected for farm trials. All three lines may be useful as donors in the basmati rice improvement program. □

Saleem and Satya released for Andhra Pradesh, India

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Saleem and Satya were released for general cultivation in 1987 for Andhra Pradesh, particularly for Telangana region. Semidwarf Saleem, derived from GEB 24/Sigadis//IR8/RNR8102, has 135 d duration in monsoon. It will grow in winter with irrigation. From 1972 to 1982, it yielded 6.4 t/ha average in monsoon, 27% more than Jaya, Jagannath, and Prakash. In winter, it registered 7.5 t/ha, 10.8% more than Jaya and Sona. In farmers' fields over 7 districts, it outyielded Tella Hamsa and Mahsuri by 21%. It has long slender grains with length:breadth ratio 3.5.

Satya, from the cross Tella Hamsa/Rasi, has 120 d duration in monsoon and 130 d in winter and

tolerates cold in vegetative phase. It tolerates bacterial blight and sheath blight. It has white long slender grains. From 1980 to 1986, it produced 5.4 t/ha

in monsoon and 5.0 t/ha in winter, 14.3% more than Tella Hamsa in monsoon and 38.4% more than Tella Hamsa and IR50 in winter. □

Mutant glutinous rice variety Xiang-zao-nou 1

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Xiang-zao-nou 1 is a new glutinous rice variety with good quality, high yields, and multiple resistance. It was developed by irradiating F₂ dry seeds of IR29/ Wen-Xwan-qing with 27.9 kR of ⁶⁰Co-gamma rays.

Xiang-zao-nou 1 has good plant type, desirable yielding components, and wide adaptability. It matures in 117 d in the early season in Hunan Province, China. Generally, it can yield 6.75 t/ha in the

early season or 6 t/ha in late season. It is highly resistant to bacterial blight and blast, and is very good in grain quality and glutinosity. This variety was grown on more than 220,000 ha 1983-87. □

P.837 — a promising new rice variety for Pondicherry, India

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In Pondicherry region (11°45' - 12°15' N and 79°35' - 80°00' E), half the crop area is planted to rice Aug-Sep to Dec-